

IMPROVED IMPACT STRENGTH OF STYRENE-METHYL METHACRYLATE COPOLYMER SHEET BY GRAFTED DEPROTEINIZED NATURAL RUBBER

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Keywords: *Poly(methyl methacrylate), DPNR-g-S/MMA, S-co-MMA sheet*

Abstract

This research was studied to improve impact strength of styrene-methyl methacrylate copolymer sheet (S-co-MMA sheet) by using deproteinized natural rubber (DPNR) as an impact modifier. High Ammoniated Natural rubber latex (HANR) (60% DRC) was prepared to protein removal by sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and followed by centrifugation. The influence of various sodium dodecyl sulfate and speed of centrifugation were investigated. Then grafted styrene and MMA onto DPNR via emulsion polymerization (DPNR-g-S/MMA). The effects of DPNR-g-S/MMA were studied by varying the amount of SDS and redox initiator. The DPNR-g-S/MMA was used as impact modifier in S-co-MMA sheet and studied the impact strength of S-co-MMA sheet. The result demonstrated the total lowest nitrogen content at $0.034 \pm 0.01\%$ with SDS 1.0 phr, centrifugation at 12,000 rpm. Moreover, grafting efficiency of DPNR-g-S/MMA was higher than NR-g-S/MMA which transmission electron micrograph was found core-shell particle in DPNR-g-S/MMA, by DPNR as core and S/MMA as shell. The result was corresponding in increasing impact strength of S-co-MMA with DPNR-g-S/MMA. The hardness Shore D was decreased because of DPNR-g-S/MMA was an elastomer which shifted the brittle S-co-MMA sheet to ductile property. The smooth fracture surface of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-g-S/MMA was found in scanning electron micrographs which assured that DPNR-g-S/MMA could be able to improve impact strength and compatibility in S-co-MMA sheet.

1. Introduction

Poly(methyl methacrylate) or acrylic sheet (PMMA) is a thermoplastic, which is widely used in many fields such as automobile parts, laminated glass and transparent roofs. With the excellent properties of PMMA, such as transparency, lightness, however, the price of methyl methacrylate monomer (MMA) is high. In order to decrease the cost of PMMA sheet production, styrene was chosen to solve the problem. The styrene-methyl methacrylate copolymer sheet (S-co-MMA sheet) is an optical clarity but styrene is very brittle, caused the lower impact strength [1]. The useful method is to modify plastic with rubber-toughening process. However, the compatibility between brittle plastic and rubber material was very low. One method to modify the rubber was graft copolymerization with a given vinyl monomer. The grafted rubber could improve the compatibility of plastics so that impact strength was modified [2-6]. Graft copolymerization has attracted much attention and is applicable to a new class of

specialty polymers with an expanded useful range. Moreover, graft copolymerization achieves heat resistance and decreasing ozonization. Natural rubber (NR) was approved to modify because of the excellent properties such as high resilience, high elongation at breaks and good fatigue resistance. However, the nitrogenous substance existing in the protein could terminate free-radical species in the grafting copolymerization process. Many researchers have noted that removal protein can improve higher grafting efficiency. There were many methods for removing protein which was enhanced the grafting efficiency. S. Kawahara *et al.* prepared deproteinized natural rubber (DPNR) by using proteolytic enzyme with surfactant followed by centrifugation, called enzymatic deproteinize natural rubber (E-DPNR). It was found that E-DPNR might be possible to achieve not only high conversion but also high grafting efficiency of monomer for the NR graft copolymerization in latex form [2]. N. Pukkate *et al.* reported that U-DPNR prepared by using urea with surfactant followed by centrifugation could be

decreased the nitrogen content from 0.35 to 0.02%w/w similar to enzymatic process. The highest conversion and grafting efficiency of styrene for U-DPNR-*g*-PS copolymer were achieved at feed of styrene 1.5 mol/kg-rubber and grafting efficiency was more than 90%w/w [3]. C. Nakason *et al.* reported that grafting efficiency of DPNR with MMA has higher than NR because proteins play an important role in free-radical polymerization. That is, the free-radical species may be terminated by proteins during graft copolymerization [4-5]. S. H. C. Man *et al.* reported that graft polymerization of vinyl monomer in DPNR latex using ammonium peroxy disulfate as catalyst was successfully prepared with more than 99% conversion [6]. While J. Sakdapipanich reported that using surfactant with centrifugation at ultra-high speed can removed protein from NR and was similar to that of an enzymatic treatment [7].

This research was studied to improve impact strength of styrene-methyl methacrylate copolymer sheet (S-co-MMA sheet) by grafted deproteinized natural rubber (DPNR-*g*-S/MMA) as an impact modifier. The S-co-MMA sheet was prepared by bulk polymerization via casting process under atmospheric condition. The impact strength and Shore D hardness of S-co-MMA sheet was also investigated.

2. Materials and Experimental

2.1 Materials

High ammoniated natural rubber latex (HANR) (60% dry rubber content) was produced by Thai Rubber Latex Co., Ltd. Cumenehydroperoxide, potassium hydroxide, tetraethylenepentamine, isopropanol and ethanol were the products of Fluka. Sodium dodecyl sulfate was purchased from Ajax Finechem. Methyl methacrylate monomer, styrene, benzoyl peroxide (BPO), azo-bis-2,4-dimethyl valeronitrile (ABVN) were supplied by Pan Asia Industrial Co., Ltd. Acetone and petroleum ether were purchased from Fisher Scientific.

2.2 Preparation of deproteinized natural rubber latex

High ammoniated natural rubber latex (HANR) (60% DRC) was removed protein by adding sodium dodecyl sulfate with various SDS at 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00 and 1.50 phr and followed by high speed refrigerated centrifugator three times at 9,000 and 12,000 rpm (Tomy Suprema 21)

2.3 Characterization of deproteinized natural rubber latex

The total nitrogen content of DPNR was characterized by elemental CHNS/O analyzer 2400 (Perkin Elmer series 2) and Fourier Transform–Infrared Spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific Nicolet 6700).

2.4 Graft copolymerization of DPNR

The grafted styrene and MMA onto DPNR via emulsion polymerization was synthesized in 500 ml five-necked round-bottomed flask equipped with mechanical stirrer, thermometer, reflux condenser and gas inlet tube. The 150 g DPNR latex was introduced into the glass reactor with SDS as an emulsifier, isopropanol as a stabilizer and potassium hydroxide to maintain the pH of the system. The system was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere at room temperature. The monomer mixture (S:MMA = 25:75 w/w) was charged into the reactor. When temperature was heated up to 70 °C, the redox initiator (CHP/TEPA) was gradually dropped. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 8 hour with under continuous stirring. The grafted DPNR latex was coagulated with ethanol and dried in vacuum oven at 60 °C. The appropriate quantities of SDS and redox initiator were also investigated.

2.5 Characterization of DPNR-*g*-S/MMA

The grafting efficiency of DPNR-*g*-S/MMA was determined by Soxhlet extraction method using petroleum ether and acetone for extracted free DPNR and copolymer, respectively. The grafting efficiency was calculated gravimetrically by the relationship following as the equation (1)

$$\%GE = \frac{\text{weight of grafted S/MMA}}{\text{weight of total S/MMA}} \times 100 \dots\dots(1)$$

when *GE* is the grafting efficiency

The DPNR-*g*-S/MMA from Soxhlet extraction method was characterized by Fourier Transform – Infrared Spectrometer and investigated core-shell particles by Transmission Electron Microscopy technique (JEOL JEM-1230).

2.6 Preparation S-co-MMA sheet containing DPNR-*g*-S/MMA

DPNR-*g*-S/MMA (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5 and 3.0 phr) was dissolved in the mixture of styrene and MMA monomer (S:MMA ratio 10:90, 20:80, 30:70 and 40:60). The mixture was stirred to get well

homogeneous solution. The radical bulk polymerization of styrene and MMA with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA was carried out by using 0.1% BPO and 0.03% ABVN as an initiator at 80 °C with continuous stirring. The homogeneous mixture was then poured into casting cell, that consisted of two glass plates with PVC spacer. Then, left casting cell into water bath at 60 °C for 4 hour. Casting cell was placed in an oven at 110 °C for 2 hour to complete the polymerization. The S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA was ejected from the glass-mold after cooling at room temperature.

2.7 Impact strength and Shore D hardness of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA

The impact strength both Izod and Charpy type were determined following ASTM D 256 and ASTM D 6110. Izod and Charpy impact strength were measured on a CEAST Model No.6957 impact tester.

The Shore D hardness was measured following ASTM D 2240 using Yasuda Model No.7047.

2.8 Scanning electron micrographs of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA

The morphology of impact fracture surfaces were characterized using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL Model JSM-5410 LV).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Characterization of deproteinized natural rubber

The results illustrate that the lowest nitrogen content as shown in Table 1 was about 0.034±0.01% which prepared by adding SDS at 1.00 phr, centrifugation at 12,000 rpm. It was found that the amount of SDS was increased, the total nitrogenous was decreased which corresponding in intensity of N-H stretching at wave number 3280 cm⁻¹ of DPNR at 12,000 rpm as shown in Fig. 1. The results from FT-IR spectra and CHNS/O analysis showed that the total nitrogen content decreased with increasing the amount of SDS. Therefore SDS could be able to remove protein from NR similar to enzyme and urea [2-4, 7].

3.2 Characterization of DPNR-*g*-S/MMA

The grafting efficiency of S/MMA copolymer onto the DPNR was higher than that of the NR according to Fig. 2. It was found that the highest grafting efficiency was 95% from emulsion polymerization with initiator of 1.00 phr [9].

The particle of DPNR-*g*-S/MMA in Fig. 3 (b) was composed of DPNR as core and S/MMA as shell.

The surface morphology of the grafted DPNR was studied by OsO₄ staining at the carbon-carbon double bonds of the DPNR to increase contrast and gradation of the DPNR particle [10].

3.3 Impact strength and Shore D hardness of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA

The impact strength of S-co-MMA sheet increased with increasing the amount of DPNR-*g*-S/MMA as shown in Fig. 4 both izod and charpy testing because of the compatibility between S-co-MMA sheet and DPNR. The highest impact strength of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA was S:MMA ratio 30:70 with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA 2.0 phr. It was found that DPNR-*g*-S/MMA could be use as an impact modifier [11].

The Shore D hardness as shown in Fig. 5 was indicated the reduction caused DPNR-*g*-S/MMA because of DPNR-*g*-S/MMA was an elastomer which was gradually shifted the brittle copolymer sheet to ductile property when the amount of graft copolymer was increased [12].

3.4 Scanning electron micrographs of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA

Scanning electron micrographs of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA were shown in Fig. 6. The smooth fracture surface was occurred in S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA. The DPNR-*g*-S/MMA could be use as an interfacial agent and compatibilizer with S-co-MMA sheet. This assured that DPNR-*g*-S/MMA can improve impact strength and compatibility of S-co-MMA sheet.

4. Conclusions

DPNR was successfully prepared by adding surfactant at SDS 1.00 phr, centrifugation at 12,000 rpm. FT-IR spectra of DPNR showed N-H stretching at wave number 3280 cm⁻¹. DPNR was used to prepare graft copolymer with styrene and methyl methacrylate via emulsion polymerization using CHP/TEPA as redox initiator. Grafting efficiency of DPNR was higher than NR because protein in NR can terminate free-radical species during graft copolymerization. The morphology of DPNR-*g*-S/MMA was core-shell particle of grafted DPNR by DPNR as core and S/MMA copolymer as shell. The DPNR-*g*-S/MMA can be used as an impact modifier in S-co-MMA sheet. The result indicated S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-*g*-S/MMA was higher impact strength than S-co-MMA sheet without DPNR-*g*-S/MMA. Because of DPNR-*g*-

S/MMA was an interfacial agent which indicated the compatibility in S-co-MMA sheet and improved the impact strength of S-co-MMA sheet. The higher impact strength of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-g-S/MMA was agree by industry and could be use in applications such as sign board and roof. Therefore DPNR-g-S/MMA could be able to use as an impact modifier in S-co-MMA sheet.

5. Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express their gratitude to Industrial Technology Assistance Program (iTAP), National Science and Technology Development Agency, the Graduate College, Industrial Chemistry Department, Faculty of Applied Science King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok Thailand for partial financial support. The authors wish to thank Pan Asia Industrial Co., Ltd. for supplying the materials, equipment and laboratory used in this research.

Table 1 Total nitrogen content of DPNR

SDS (phr)	The total nitrogen content (%w/w)	
	Centrifuge at 9000 rpm	Centrifuge at 12000 rpm
0.00	0.442±0.01	0.331±0.01
0.25	0.394±0.01	0.213±0.01
0.50	0.244±0.01	0.153±0.03
0.75	0.209±0.01	0.078±0.01
1.00	0.136±0.01	0.034±0.01
1.50	0.135±0.02	0.033±0.02

Fig. 1 FT-IR spectra of DPNR with various SDS.
 (a) DPNR (Control) (b) SDS 0.25 phr
 (c) SDS 0.50 phr (d) SDS 0.75 phr
 (e) SDS 1.00 phr (f) SDS 1.50 phr

Fig. 2 Grafting efficiency of NR-g-S/MMA and DPNR-g-S/MMA

Fig. 3 TEM micrographs of (x 15,000)
 (a) DPNR (b) DPNR-g-S/MMA

Fig. 4 Impact strength of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-g-S/MMA at 2.0 phr and various S:MMA ratio.

Fig. 5 Shore D Hardness of S-co-MMA sheet with DPNR-g-S/MMA

Fig. 6 SEM micrographs of (x 750)
 (a) S:MMA at 30:70
 (b) S:MMA:gDPNR at 30:70:2.0

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